

Advisory Committee (AC) Offboarding Guide

Name: []

Personal email: []

Offboarding date: []

Person responsible for this offboarding process: []

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1. Introduction

Offboarding is the process through which a person disengages from their role and ceases to be part of the MetaDocencia Advisory Committee. To begin the process, you must inform the Chair of the Advisory Committee, through Slack and via email, of your decision to leave, preferably with a minimum notice period of 30 days.

The person responsible for your offboarding process will help you leave resources shared with your individual and group accounts in an orderly manner, following the actions recommended in this document.

Offboarding from the MetaDocencia Advisory Committee does not imply the need to stop participating in public activities in the community unless the team responsible for ensuring compliance with the MetaDocencia Community Guidelines determines otherwise.

Below, you and the person responsible for your offboarding will find checklists to follow so that the process is completed smoothly.

2. Tasks for the person who is being offboarded

- Inform the MetaDocencia Advisory Committee Chair about your decision to no longer hold your position, if applicable, via email and Slack.
- If you are participating in any Advisory Council activities that have not yet been completed, agree with the Advisory Committee chair on how to delegate your tasks.
- If you have used Trello, review the tasks and checklist items assigned to you and agree with one or more people on the team to transfer any pending tasks.
- Notify if you agree to maintain your profile on the MetaDocencia website, in the “Outside Contributors” or “Former Contributors” sections, as appropriate.
- Update your ORCID profile, LinkedIn, CV, and other similar records (if you have them) with the ending date of your role on the MetaDocencia Advisory Committee.
- If you find any tools or services that you still have access to after this process is complete, please contact the person responsible for your offboarding to remove your access.

- Share an email address if you want MetaDocencia to contact you in the future.
 - If you would rather not be contacted in the future, please notify the person responsible for your offboarding.
- Complete a [self reflection exercise](#) (optional).
- Schedule an exit call with the person responsible for your offboarding.
 - An exit call provides the opportunity to share feedback about your experience as a member of the Advisory Committee.
 - Any agenda and notes documents shared on this call must be accessible from a personal email of the person who is being offboarded.
- Sign any documents required by the fiscal sponsor to record the offboarding.

3. Tasks for the person responsible for the offboarding

- Create a folder for the person being offboarded within [this directory](#), with a copy of this guide. Name the folder “[First Name Last Name] AC Offboarding Guide”.
- Review with the fiscal sponsor that there were no changes in the requirements for an Advisory Committee member offboarding.
- Update MetaDocencia governance documents and remove the name of the person who is leaving where appropriate.
- Give access to the offboarding documents to a personal email of the person who is leaving their role. Keep in mind that in the future they will not have access to documents shared in MetaDocencia’s drive.
- Carefully review whether at the end of the offboarding process the person who is leaving still has access to any tools or services and, if this is the case, notify the Infrastructure team.

4. Tasks for the Infrastructure Team

- Update the website, moving the person to the “Outside Contributors” or “Former Contributors” section, as appropriate.

- Google Drive: terminate the offboarded member's access to the [Advisory Committee Google Drive shared drive](#).
- Google Groups: remove the offboarded member's email account from the email list advisorycommittee@metadocencia.org.
- Slack: remove the offboarded member from the [#advisory-committee](#) channel and any other private channels where they were included due to particular circumstances of serving the AC.

5. Tasks for the Advisory Committee Chair

- Notify via Slack on channels #advisory-committee and #colaboradores that the person will no longer be part of the AC as of the agreed date.
- Update a copy of the document [Project Advisory Committee Table](#) with new AC member's data.
- Send the updated copy of the table to our fiscal sponsor, CS&S.

6. How Can We Improve?

We want to hear your opinion on this offboarding process and on your time at MetaDocencia. Please complete this [anonymous offboarding survey](#). Your observations are very valuable and help us improve our processes!

Thank you very much for all your contributions to MetaDocencia! 🍌

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References

- MetaDocencia, 2023. [Guía de incorporación Consejo Asesor \(CA\)](#).
- Malvika Sharan, 2022. [Offboarding handbook for the members of governance and other key groups in Open Life Science](#). Adapted from the original work of the International Labour Office (ILO).